

Chelating Behaviour of a new Pyrazolylacetohydrazide : *Bis-* Complexes of Nickel(II) with α -[3,5, Dimethyl-1-Pyrazolyl]acetohydrazide.

NITYANANDA SAHA* and DIPAK BHATTACHARYYA

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratories, Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009.

The coordination behaviour of a new Pyrazolylacetohydrazide, α -[3,5-Dimethyl-1-Pyrazolyl] acetohydrazide (synthesised in the laboratory) has been reported by complexation with Nickel(II) salts. *Bis*-Complexes of the type $Ni(PAH)_2X_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($X = Cl, Br, NO_3, SCN, \frac{1}{2}SO_4$) have been characterised from magnetic and diffuse reflectance spectral data in the solid state and molar conductance and electronic spectral data in solution. All the nickel(II) complexes are octahedral as evident from spectral data and the corresponding ligandfield parameters calculated in terms of O_h symmetry. I. R. spectra of the ligand and the complexes have indicated the pyrazole-ring nitrogen and the amidinitrogen (involving and imidol structure) of the hydrazide residue as the points of attachment showing neutral bidentate of the ligand.

ACID hydrazides are well-known for their antituberculous activity¹ and offer potential binding sites for metal ions. Pyrazole derivatives, on the other hand, have long been known for their medicinal values and recently, certain pyrazole-pyrimidines are being studied in the fight against cancer². With a view to build up a pyrazole derivative containing a hydrazide residue, which might have potential biological importance, we have synthesised α -[3,5-Dimethyl-1-Pyrazolyl] acetohydrazide (I, henceforth abbreviated as PAH) and investigated its chelating behaviour by complex formation with transition metal ions. The present communication reports the isolation of *bis*-complexes of the type

$Ni(PAH)_2X_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($X = Cl, Br, NO_3, SCN, \frac{1}{2}SO_4$) and their characterisation through elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temperature, diffuse reflectance spectra and vibrational spectral data in the solid state; and molar conductance values and electronic spectra in solution.

Experimental

(A) Preparation of the ligand :

α -(3,5-Dimethyl-1-Pyrazolyl) acetohydrazide was prepared from the reaction of ethyl-3,5-Dimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetate³ with hydrazine hydrate.

Ethyl-3,5-Dimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetate (0.1 mole ; 18.2 gm) in ethanol (50 ml) was made to react with 99-100% hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mole ; 5 gm), the later being added dropwise with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was heated on the waterbath for about 30 minutes. It was then cooled in an ice-bath ; white shining compound separated with time ; it was filtered off, washed well with aqueous alcohol and finally dried in a desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$.

Recrystallisation from ethanol yielded white shining crystals, m.p. 198°C.

Anal. Found : C, 49.90 ; H, 7.03 ; N, 33.30%

Calcd. for $C_7H_{12}N_4O$: C, 49.99 ; H, 7.19 ; N, 33.32%

(B) Preparation of the Nickel (II) Complexes :

(i) $Ni(PAH)_2X_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($X = Cl, Br$)

On mixing ethanolic solutions of nickel halide hexahydrate (0.005 mole) and the ligand (0.01 mole), a blue solution resulted ($pH \approx 3$). The reaction mixture was heated on the water-bath until evaporated nearly to dryness ; *n*-butanol (10 ml) was added to it and was left at room temperature for slow evaporation. A blue micro-crystalline compound separated out in each case, within ~ 12 hours. It was filtered off, washed with ethanol and then dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$.

(ii) $Ni(PAH)_2X_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($X = NO_3, \frac{1}{2}SO_4$) :

The corresponding metal salt hydrate (0.005 mole) dissolved in aqueous alcohol was mixed with a hot

alcoholic solution of the ligand (0.01 mole) a blue solution resulted ($pH \approx 3$). This was cooled in ice with occasional stirring when light blue compound precipitated; this was collected as before.

(iii) $Ni(PAH)_2(SCN)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$:

Ethanol solution of the hydrated nickel(II) nitrate (0.005 mole) and KSCN (0.01 mole) were mixed and the precipitated KNO_3 was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to a smaller bulk and finally filtered directly into a hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mole). The reaction mixture was stirred well when pale blue compound separated: this was collected in the usual manner.

Physico-chemical measurements and the instruments used :

The electronic diffuse reflectance spectra were taken in a Ziess PMQ II Spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment RA3. Electronic Spectra in Spekpure solvents were recorded in a Hilger UVISPEK Spectrophotometer using 1 cm. cell. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured in a Gouy balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as calibrant. The molar conductances were measured in a Philips PR 9500 type conductivity bridge. The I.R. spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes were recorded in Beckman '20' I.R. Spectrophotometer using KBr pellets.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data along with other characteristic properties like colour, molar conductance and effective magnetic moment values of the complexes are placed in Table-1 while the results on the spectral analyses are given in Table-2.

All these pale blue nickel(II) complexes are readily soluble in water, low molecular weight alcohols and in common organic solvents. The molar conductance values (Λ_m) of the compounds in conductivity water indicate their ionic nature atleast in aqueous solution.

The room temperature magnetic moments of all the complexes (Table 1) fall within the rangs 2.83-3.4 B.M. expected for six-coordinate spin-free nickel(II) complexes⁴. The observed deviation in magnetic moments from the spin-only value could be due to the second order Zeeman effects between the ground state and the highest ligand field terms.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the present nickel(II) complexes (Fig. 1 & 2) are characterised by

Fig. 1

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, FORMULAE AND OTHER PROPERTIES OF THE $Ni(PAH)_2 \cdot x \cdot 2H_2O$ COMPOUNDS

Complex	Colour	% Ni		% Nitrogen		% Anion		μ_{eff} in B.M. (301°K)	Molar conductance, Λ_m ($ohm^{-1} \cdot cm^2 \cdot mole^{-1}$) in $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution in conductivity water at 30°C
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found		
I. $Ni(PAH)_2Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	greenish blue	11.69	11.63	22.33	22.19	14.12	14.03 [†]	3.11	221.9
II. $Ni(PAH)_2Br_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	pale blue	9.93	9.88	18.97	18.91	27.04	27.12 [†]	3.07	262.0
III. $Ni(PAH)_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	pale blue	10.57	10.55	25.23 [*]	25.34	—	—	3.06	235.2
IV. $Ni(PAH)_2(SCN)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	pale blue	10.73	10.69	25.60 ^{**}	25.76	11.71 ^{***}	11.58	3.17	265.3
V. $Ni(PAH)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	pale blue	11.14	11.17	21.26	21.21	18.22	18.30 [†]	3.21	202.2

† Estimated gravimetrically as silver halide
 * Including nitrogen present in nitrate
 ** Including nitrogen present in thiocyanate
 *** Percentage of sulphur (estimated gravimetrically as $BaSO_4$)
 ‡ Estimated gravimetrically as $BaSO_4$
 PAH=a molecule of α -(3,5-Dimethyl-1-Pyrazolyl) acetohydrazide.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF Ni(PAH)₂x₂.2H₂O

Complex	Medium	Colour of the solution	Absorption maxima in cm ⁻¹ (ε molar for solns.)
I. Ni(PAH) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	(i) Reflectance	—	25,800 ; 15,600 ; 14,200 sh ; 9,800 br ; 7,000 br-sh.
	(ii) Methanol	blue	26310 (10.48) ; 15,160 (6.41) ; 13,160 sh(2.93).
II. Ni(PAH) ₂ Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	(i) Reflectance	—	25,400 ; 16,800 ; 10,100 ; 6,200.
	(ii) Methanol	blue	26,310 (8.98) ; 16,000 (5.96) ; 13,330 sh(2.75).
III. Ni(PAH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O	(i) Reflectance	—	26,000 ; 17,000 ; 10,800 ; 6,400 ; 5,800 sh.
	(ii) Methanol	blue	26,310 (9.05) ; 16,000 (5.76) ; 13,330 sh (2.14) ; 10,000 (8.23).
IV. Ni(PAH) ₂ (SCN) ₂ .2H ₂ O	(i) Reflectance	—	26,000 ; 21,600 sh ; 16,600 ; 13,200 sh ; 10,500 ; 6,400
	(ii) Methanol	blue	25,970 (15.9) ; 16,000 (8.41) ; 13,330 sh(2.56).
V. Ni(PAH) ₂ SO ₄ .2H ₂ O	(i) Reflectance	—	26,000 ; 16,800 ; 10,800 ; 5,800.
	(ii) Methanol	blue	25,970 (6.64) ; 16,000 (5.65) ; 13,160 sh (2.93) ; 10,210 (7.66).

br = broad ; sh = shoulder.

Fig. 2

three principal bands appearing at ~10,000, 15,000-17,000 and ~26,000 cm⁻¹ which can be ascribed to the spin-allowed transitions, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}(ν₁), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F)(ν₂) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P)(ν₃) respectively in good agreement with those predicted from Liehr and Ballhausen⁵ energy level diagram for Ni(II) ions in O_h symmetry. The ligand field parameters, Dq (taken directly from the ν₁ transition), B (calculated from known relationship⁶) and β(B/1080) together with the theoretical ν₂ band position (calculated from known relationship⁷) and ν₂/ν₁ ratio are given in Table 3.

The results are more or less in good agreement with those reported for octahedral nickel(II) complexes⁸. The ν₂/ν₁ ratio of 1.55-1.66 (Table-3) characterises all the nickel(II) complexes as essentially having pseudo-octahedral environments, evidently suggesting strong T_{1g} term interactions⁹. Moreover, the absence of any recognizable splitting in the absorption bands and

TABLE 3—PRINCIPAL BAND POSITIONS IN THE REFLECTANCE SPECTRA WITH PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS AND THE LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS.

Complex	Band positions (cm ⁻¹)			Dq in cm ⁻¹	B in cm ⁻¹	β *	ν ₂ Calcd. in cm ⁻¹	ν ₂ /ν ₁
	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (ν ₁)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F)(ν ₂)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P)(ν ₃)					
I. Ni(PAH) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	9,800	15,600	25,800	980	800	0.74	15,760	1.59
II. Ni(PAH) ₂ Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	10,100	16,800	25,400	1010	793	0.73	16,040	1.66
III. Ni(PAH) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .2H ₂ O	10,800	17,000	26,000	1080	707	0.65	16,700	1.57
IV. Ni(PAH) ₂ (SCN) ₂ .2H ₂ O	10,500	16,600	26,000	1050	740	0.69	16,415	1.58
V. Ni(PAH) ₂ SO ₄ .2H ₂ O	10,800	16,800	26,000	1080	693	0.64	16,700	1.55

* β = B/B₀ = B/1080 (where B₀ = the Racah parameter value in the free ion state)

[B. N. Figgis : "Introduction to Ligand Fields", John Wiley and Sons., N. Y. p. 234 (1967)]

a more or less fair agreement between the calculated and observed ν_2 bands (Table 3) serve as good evidences for O_h symmetry in the present nickel (II) complexes¹⁰. However, in most of the cases, the calculated value for ν_2 is lower than the observed one, which could be attributed to a smaller interaction of the T_{1g} terms than could be expected for a pure octahedral case¹⁰.

The origin of the weak broad band at $\sim 6000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in some complexes is not definitely known; it may conceivably arise from ligand overtone modes.

In addition to three usual spin-allowed bands (Table 2) in the reflectance spectrum of $\text{Ni}(\text{PAH})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the broad shoulder appearing at $\sim 7000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may probably result from some lowering in symmetry¹¹.

Although the ν_1' bands in the solution spectra could not be located due to the limited range of the spectrometer used, nevertheless the positions of ν_2 and ν_3 bands along with their molar extinction values (3-10) evidently point to an overall octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes in methanol solution, suggesting no gross change on dissolution.

The weak shoulders appearing around $\sim 13,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in both solid and solution spectra of some of the complexes may be assigned to spin-forbidden transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ (D) as suggested earlier¹².

I. R. Spectra: The ligand, α -(3,5-dimethyl-1-para-lyl) acetohydrazide has been characterised by the i. r. spectral bands. Two distinguishable bands at 3300 (s) and 3200 (ms) have been assigned to the NH and NH, stretchin: frequencies¹³ of the hydrazide residue. The broad band at 1660-1630 (bs) cm^{-1} in the free ligand may be considered as amide-I stretching vibration associated with the vibration due to β (NH_2). The strong

band at 1520 cm^{-1} is ascribed to ν ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) of the pyrazole ring, while the band at $1265\text{ (ssh)}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to amide-III stretching vibration for the molecule.

The acetohydrazide group in position I of the pyrazole ring may coordinate to a metal ion either in an enolic form¹⁴ (II) or in the ketonic one¹⁵ (III).

Since all the present nickel(II) complexes of the ligand molecule (PAH) are prepared in solutions of high hydrogen ion concentration (pH 3) and all of them behaved as typical electrolytes in solution (as 1:2 in water), so the possibility of the hydrazide residue to act in the enolic form (II) involving deprotonation may be excluded as suggested earlier by Sacconi¹⁵.

The most remarkable change that occurs in the i. r. spectra of the metal complexes as compared to the free ligand is the displacement of the amide-I band with the simultaneous appearance of three new bands at ~ 1600 , ~ 1300 and $\sim 1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table:4). This implies that the coordination to the metal ion in the complexes must occur either through carbonyl oxygen (Structure IV) or through the amide nitrogen (Structure V) with an 'imidol' structure of the hydrazide residue.

TABLE 4—SOME CHARACTERISTIC STRETCHING FREQUENCIES IN THE I. R. SPECTRA OF $\text{Ni}(\text{PAH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ TOGETHER WITH THE LIGAND

Possible band stretches (in cm^{-1})	PAH	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAH})_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAH})_2 \cdot \text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAH})_2 \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAH})_2 \cdot (\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAH})_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
Amide I & β (NH_2)	1660-1630bs	1660ms	1645s	1650s	1665sh 1645s	1665s
$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$	—	1600ms	1600s	1600ms	1600s	1600ms
$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$	1520s	1550ms	1540ms	1540ms	1540ms	1550s
$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$	—	1285ms	1290ms	1300ssh	1540ms	1300s
Amide III	1265ssh	—	—	—	1290s	—
$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-)$	—	1050s	1050ms	1050ms	—	1060s
NH_2 -deformation	1020w	1030sh	1025w	1035ms	1030sh	1040sh

* ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) means ${}^2\text{N}$ of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ in $-\text{CH}_2-\overset{\text{HO}}{\underset{|}{\text{C}}}=\overset{2}{\text{N}}-\overset{1}{\text{NH}}_2$

** ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) means ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) pyrazole ring.

The i. r. spectral data of the present complexes point to the structure V as has been suggested by Jabalpurwala et al¹⁶ in their studies on the metal complexes of salicyloyl hydrazide.

In all the complexes, the extra newly developed band at 1050-1060 cm⁻¹ can safely be assigned to ν (C-O)¹⁷ which does support the structure V. It may be pointed out that for structure IV, there should not have any new band in this region. The newly developed i.r. bands at \sim 1600 and \sim 1300 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes are assigned to ν_{asym} (C=N) and ν_{sym} (C=N) respectively¹⁸, which further points to the 'imidol' structure of the hydrazide residue, indicating the participation of ¹⁵N atom of the C=N group in the complex formation with metal ions (structure V). Conversely, if the band at \sim 1300 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes is attributed to amide-III band in agreement with structure IV, then the observed positive shifts (Table 4) are difficult to explain.

The i.r. spectra of the metal complexes in the 3 μ region are rather complicated probably due to the overlap of the NH and NH₂ stretching vibrations along with those of O-H mode of the attached water molecules present in all the complexes. The broad diffused nature of the band, showing no appreciable shift to the lower frequency side as compared to the free ligand molecule, suggests the non-involvement of the terminal nitrogen (¹⁵N) atom of the hydrazide residue in complex formation and may arise from extensive hydrogen bonding (intra or/and intermolecular) in the complexes.

In view of the X-ray crystallography of several pyrazole-metal complexes¹⁹, it may reasonably be taken that the tertiary nitrogen atom of the pyrazole ring in the ligand molecule (PAH), is obviously another point of attachment to the metal in its metal complexes. Although direct evidence for this M-N bonding could not be presented due to the absence of data in the far i.r. region, nevertheless, this can indirectly be inferred from the shifts of the C=N vibration of the pyrazole ring in the metal complexes towards higher frequency side (1550-1560 cm⁻¹) as compared to that (1520 cm⁻¹) in the uncomplexed ligand, showing involvement of the tertiary nitrogen atom of the pyrazole in complexation. Similar positive shifts have also been noticed for the transition metal complexes of other heterocyclic bases^{20,21}. The mode of attachment of the anion in the complexes can also be qualitatively inferred from i.r. spectra.

Nitrate complex: The appearance of bands at 1375 (vs), 1350 (sh), 1035 (ms) and 760 (s) cm⁻¹ in the i. r. spectrum of Ni(PAH)₂(NO₃)₂.2H₂O clearly suggests the monodentate behavior of nitrate group in C_{2v} symmetry²².

Thiocyanate complexes: The i. r. spectrum of this complex exhibits strong bands at 2095 cm⁻¹ (ν C-N) and 805 cm⁻¹ (ν C-S) which confirms the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate groups in the complex²³.

Sulphate complex: The i. r. spectrum of the complex shows medium sharp bands at 1180 cm⁻¹ and 960 cm⁻¹ along with a sharp band at 605 cm⁻¹ which points to the ionic nature of the sulphate group with T_d symmetry in the complex²⁴.

Thus, from the above discussion, it is reasonable to take that the anion (X) is preferentially coordinated in Ni(PAH)₂X₂.2H₂O in the solid state [except Ni(PAH)₂SO₄.2H₂O] and the complexes undergo extensive solvolysis in water which account for their high molar conductance (Λ_m) values in the said solvent. This may be schemetically represented as :

where X = Cl, Br, NO₃, SCN.

It appears, therefore, that the ligand, α -(3-5-Dimethyl-1-Pyrazolyl) acetohydrazide, in general, exhibits a neutral bidentate function through the tertiary nitrogen of the pyrazole ring and the amide nitrogen (involving an imidol structure, V) of the hydrazide residue in forming the bis-complexes of nickel(II) having the general composition Ni(PAH)₂X₂.2H₂O.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. S. E. Livingstone of the University of New South Wales, Australia for kindly providing them with the reflectance spectra of the compounds.

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